

Priority pathogens of fungal and bacterial infections: development trends and impact on the epidemiological situation in the Russian Federation

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY: This review analyzes the epidemiological situation of fungal and bacterial infections in Russia, including the identification of priority pathogens based on WHO data, their geographic distribution, impact on various age or social groups, and infection severity. The analysis covers the dynamics of infection prevalence over the past 10 years. Additionally, it examines the impact of the identified trends on population morbidity, mortality, and disability rates.

DATA SOURCES AND ANALYSIS: The analysis was based on official statistics from Federal Service for the Oversight of Consumer Protection and Welfare (FSOCPW, Russia), information from the WHO, and data from papers published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. It considers population morbidity and mortality rates together with factors influencing the spread of infections, namely, changes in virulence, development of antibiotic resistance, spread of resistant strains, and emerging pathogens. The data used for the assessment of infectious disease dynamics over the past 10 years also include such factors as climate change, urbanization, and migration, together with the geographic distribution of infectious diseases and their demographic impact.

CONCLUSION: The results highlight the need for continuous epidemiological monitoring, development of new strategies for the prevention and treatment of infectious diseases and strengthening of measures to combat antibiotic resistance in Russia.

Keywords: fungal infections, bacterial infections, Russia, WHO, epidemiology, priority pathogens

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INTRODUCTION

Fungal and bacterial infections pose a serious threat to public health. In 2020 in Russia, the incidence of fungal infections was as follows: microsporia – 40.2 per 100,000 (176 per 100,000 children under 14 years old); nail, hand, and foot mycoses – 101.8 per 100,000 (149,410 cases); and onychomycosis, 68.4 per 100,000 (100,323 cases) [1]. According to data of the Russian Federal Service

for the Oversight of Consumer Protection and Welfare (FSOCPW), the incidence of shigellosis decreased to 1.76 per 100,000 population, while the incidence of salmonellosis increased by 25.44% to 21.45 per 100,000 population in 2023 [2]. The frequency of co-infections remains high: 35.96% of COVID-19 patients had a bacterial co-infection (2020), while the proportion of

fungal infections increased from 26.9% (in 2020) to 34.2% (in 2021), with candidal stomatitis predominating (71%) [3].

The irrational use of antibiotics and antifungal drugs, including the treatment of asymptomatic bacteriuria, contributes to the development of resistance and complicates the treatment. Broad-spectrum antibiotics can disrupt microbiota and promote fungal growth, especially in cases of prior yeast colonization, leading to candidiasis and other fungal infections. Changes in the spectrum of priority pathogens are driven by climate change, globalization, emergence of new strains, and widespread antibiotic use. Therefore, analyzing the spread of fungal and bacterial infections in Russia, their development trends and impact on the epidemiological situation remains highly relevant.

In 2022, the WHO published for the first time a list of 19 fungi most dangerous to humans, categorizing them into three risk levels (critical, high, and medium) [4]. In 2024, the bacterial priority pathogen list (BPPL) was updated, including 15 families of antibiotic-resistant bacteria with similar classifications based on the degree of threat [5]. These lists highlight the urgent need to develop new treatment and prevention methods aimed at overcoming the growing problem of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and serve as a basis for further research in this field.

The aim of this study was to identify the priority pathogens of fungal and bacterial infections in the Russian Federation (considering WHO classification), analyze trends in their spread and development of antibiotic resistance, assess the impact of factors contributing to the increased incidence of infections, and justify the need for new prevention and treatment strategies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study conducted a comprehensive data analysis, including a systematic review of the scientific literature (cited in PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases), an analysis of official statistical information from FSOCPW and WHO. According to the selection criteria, data from papers published in English and Russian between 2015 and 2024, focusing on the fungal and bacterial priority pathogens in Russia, their development trends, and their impact on the epidemiological situation were included in this review. Official statistical information from FSOCPW included data on the incidence of fungal and bacterial infections in Russia. WHO data were extracted from reports and publications for the period 2015–2024, covering global trends in infectious diseases and the new fungal classification.

Prioritization was performed using various methods. The WHO has successfully used multiple-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) to compile lists of priority bacterial pathogens (2017) and diseases (2018) [6]. The MCDA enables the integration of various criteria, including qualitative and quantitative data, as well as expert knowledge from stakeholders.

In this study, the iterative approach developed by the WHO was used to determine priority fungal pathogens. The process consisted of eight stages, each aimed at forming a scientifically sound list of pathogens that require attention in areas of public health and research. A multistage analysis was conducted to identify priority fungal pathogens, including the formation of expert groups, defining priority criteria, conducting broad-spectrum pathogen analysis (19 priority pathogens identified), conducting systematic reviews, application of the discrete choice experiment (DCE) method in six WHO regions (in three languages), application of the best-worst scaling (BWS) method for public health assessment, and development activities. The results were integrated into the final ranked list of fungal priority pathogens [4].

The following criteria were established for assessing priority fungal pathogens:

- Cases: average fatality rate (rank: low <30%, medium 30-70%, high >70%, unknown).
- Annual incidence: number of new cases per million people (rank: low <2, medium 2-50, high >50, unknown).
- Global distribution: geographic spread (local ≤ 2 WHO regions, global ≥ 3 WHO regions, unknown).
- Ten-year trends: changes in disease incidence (stable, increasing, unknown).
- Hospitalization: average duration of hospital stay (rank: low <2 days, medium 2 days to 2 weeks, high >2 weeks, unknown).
- Complications and outcomes: proportion of patients with long-term complications (rank: low <10%, medium 10-50%, high >50%).
- Resistance to antifungal treatment: frequency of resistance (rank: low <10%, medium >10% for 1-2 classes of antimicrobials, high >10% for 3-4 classes of antimicrobials, unknown).
- Preventability: availability of effective preventive measures (rank: low, medium, high, unknown).
- Access to diagnostic tests: availability of diagnostics (rank: low, medium, high, very high).
- Evidence-based treatment procedures: assessment of treatment availability and quality (rank: very low, low, medium, high).

The WHO fungal infection prioritization study was conducted using the DCE experiment, with the participation of 376 clinicians and researchers. In another BWS-based study, 49 WHO experts assessed the significance of pathogens in public health. Both studies were conducted ensuring gender balance and geographic representation [4].

The combined results of the DCE and BWS studies, along with systematic review data, allowed for the creation of a comprehensive pathogen ranking to guide research, development, prevention, and control strategies for infectious diseases and antifungal resistance.

Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is an effective prioritization method capable of considering a wide range of criteria and expert opinions, even in cases of incomplete or conflicting information [7, 8].

The updated WHO list of drug – bacterial pathogen priority combinations (BPPL-2024), compiled in 2024 using MCDA and the PAPRIKA (Potentially All Pairwise RanKings of all possible Alternatives) global study across six WHO regions, provides an objective and

comprehensive prioritization ranking based on eight criteria (Fig. 1).

The process begins with the conceptualization of the study and formation of the WHO advisory group (Bacterial Priority Pathogens List, BPPL AG). Next, antibiotic-resistant pathogens were selected, the evaluation criteria were refined, data were collected, and experts were identified for participation in the global PAPRIKA study. PAPRIKA examined the importance of each criterion [5]. The pathogens were then evaluated for each criterion in the MCDA matrix. The final calculations, ranking, and pathogens antibiotics sensitivity analyses complete the process, leading to the formation of the final BPPL list. The expert selection process for PAPRIKA was open, including a review of 120 applications to ensure a geographical, subject, and gender balance across all six WHO regions. A total of 23 experts were selected [9].

The WHO criteria for prioritizing antibiotic-resistant bacterial pathogens include mortality (case fatality rate), prevalence (number of cases per million people), non-fatal health burden (years lived with disability

Fig. 1. Operational definitions of priority categories in the 2024 WHO BPPL [5].

(YLD) per million people), resistance trends (10-year trend, percentage of resistant isolates), transmission potential (evidence of spread), prevention feasibility (availability and effectiveness of measures), treatability (number, effectiveness, safety, accessibility, and cost of treatments), and pipeline (number of new antibiotics and their developmental stages). The Prevention Feasibility criterion assesses individual and public health measures, including hygiene, isolation, vaccination, sanitation, and food safety. The Treatability criterion considers the number, effectiveness, safety, and availability of drugs. The Pipeline criterion evaluates future treatment options, considering new antibiotics in development.

RESULTS

Based on numerical evaluations and discussions within the WHO Fungal Priority Pathogens List (FPPL) group, all the 19 selected fungal pathogens were ranked and divided into three priority groups (Fig. 2).

- **Critical Priority Group:** *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Candida auris*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, and *Candida albicans*.
- **High Priority Group:** *Nakaseomyces glabrata* (*Candida glabrata*), *Histoplasma* spp., *Eumycetoma* causative agents, *Mucorales*, *Fusarium* spp., *Candida tropicalis*, and *Candida parapsilosis*.
- **Medium Priority Group:** *Scedosporium* spp., *Lomentospora prolificans*, *Coccidioides* spp., *Pichia kudriavzevii* (*Candida krusei*), *Cryptococcus gattii*, *Talaromyces marneffeii*, *Pneumocystis jirovecii*, and *Paracoccidioides* spp.

Research and development (R&D) priorities were determined using weighted criteria, with antifungal resistance receiving the highest weight (38.5%), followed by mortality (13.9%), availability of evidence-based treatment (11.9%), diagnostic accessibility (10.4%), annual incidence (8.5%), and complications (8.4%). Other criteria had a weight of less than 5% [10]. The ranking of each of the 19 pathogens, calculated based on the DCE method (for assessing R&D needs) and BWS evaluation (for public health significance), along with their combined ranking (weighted 0.48 (DCE) and 0.52 (BWS)), are shown in Fig. 3.

Lomentospora prolificans ranked highest in R&D needs due to the lack of effective treatment but received a low ranking in public health significance because of its low prevalence, resulting in an overall rank of 13. *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Candida albicans*, despite having lower R&D ranking, scored higher overall because of their high public health significance.

Cryptococcus neoformans is the dominant species in Russia and Europe. Research from the North-Western State Medical University named after I. I. Mechnikov reported a significant increase in cryptococcosis mortality in St. Petersburg in 2010 [11]. However, the recent mortality trends remain unknown, highlighting the need for further research. Studies conducted from 2023 to 2024 revealed that disruptions in lipid metabolism in *C. neoformans*, caused either by *opi3* gene loss (encoding methylene-fatty-acyl-phospholipid synthase) or deletion of the sterol transporter protein YSP2, lead to membrane integrity loss and reduced fungal virulence [12]. However, data on the prevalence of this fungus in Russia are lacking.

In 2021, T. Ruzhentsova (G. N. Gabrichevsky Moscow Research Institute of Epidemiology and Microbiology) stated that *C. auris* is not widespread in Russia, although isolated cases have been reported. *C. auris* has high adhesion to human skin and surfaces, enabling long-term survival in both patients and the environment. Colonization by this fungus increases the risk of candidemia, affecting 25% of the critically ill patients. A significant proportion of *C. auris* strains are resistant to fluconazole, and some of them exhibit pan-drug resistance. As of October 2024, there is no effective vaccine against this fungus [13].

The *Aspergillus* genus in Russia includes multiple species, with *Aspergillus fumigatus* being the most common, particularly in the southern regions (Krasnodar and Rostov regions). Clinically significant species also include *A. versicolor*, *A. flavus*, and *A. niger*, detected in regions such as Tatarstan (Cheremshan, Zainsk, Baltasi, Vysokogorsky, and Nizhnekamsk districts), Ulyanovsk, Saratov, and Rostov regions, as well as in Moscow and St. Petersburg. *A. fumigatus* virulence increases at high temperature and humidity and in the absence of UV radiation. Prolonged azole and fungicide use has led to antifungal resistance, as evidenced by the 2022 isolation of a voriconazole-resistant *A. fumigatus* strain carrying the TR46/Y121F/T289A mutation in *cyp51A* gene. Climate change could facilitate the spread of thermotolerant *Aspergillus* species to colder regions [14].

Candida albicans is responsible for 90–95% of urogenital candidiasis cases in Russia. It is found in 20–50% of healthy individuals' intestines, 20–60% of oral cavities, and 10–17% of vaginal microbiota in women. The risk factors for this disease include age, glucocorticosteroids or antibiotics treatment, chemotherapy, diabetes, HIV, and immunodeficiencies. High resistance rates of this fungus to fluconazole (48.8%) and voriconazole (44.8%) have decreased the efficiency of recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis treatment (RVVC, 98% of cases in 2024).

Fig. 2. WHO list of fungal priority pathogens [4].

Fig. 3. Overall fungal pathogen ranking based on MCDA stages [4].

Virulence factors: adhesion, enzymes, hyphal formation, and biofilms. *C. albicans* has been linked to an increased cancer risk [15].

A study conducted on *N. glabratus* isolated from patients in Russia between 2023 and 2024 did not reveal resistance to echinocandins; however, 5.2% of the strains showed multidrug resistance to azoles and amphotericin B [16].

Lenchenko et al. in 2024 found significant phenotypic variability in *Nakaseomyces glabrata* (formerly *Candida glabrata*) [17], including variations in antifungal susceptibility, environmental adaptation, and pathogenicity linked to biofilm formation. One isolate exhibited high resistance to caspofungin. An Iranian study analyzed 320 clinical isolates, whereas other studies showed the potential therapeutic effect of catechin in treating *N. glabrata* infections.

Histoplasmosis is considered a rare condition in Russia. Risk groups include men, children, rural workers, tourists, and immunocompromised individuals. The severity of the disease depends on the immune status, with children, the elderly, and immunocompromised individuals being the most vulnerable. Research in this area focuses on the molecular mechanisms of virulence,

including the heat shock protein Hsp60 and enolase, as well as epidemiology in horses. The high mortality among HIV-infected patients (up to 80%) underscores the need for effective screening in endemic regions [18].

Eumycetoma primarily affects young men (aged 11–30 years) who work in agriculture. This disease often causes severe quality of life impairment (60.3% of patients), leads to limb amputation (up to 38.5%), and has recurrence rates of between 31.8% and 73.5%. A systematic review published in 2024 (covering 2011–2021 data) confirmed that *eumycetoma* is a serious and widespread fungal infection. Key risk factors include male sex, young age, and occupational exposure to agriculture [19]. The prioritization of fungal pathogens in this study was based on the WHO assessment and considered both individual species and genera, which represent a group of several clinically significant pathogens. This approach is due to the complexity of accurately identifying certain species and the need to account for a wide range of pathogens that cause serious diseases. In particular, the inclusion of the Mucorales order in the high-priority group was preceded by the analysis of data on the prevalence and mortality rates of mucormycosis in Russia. Widespread species such as *Mucor hiemalis* are common in the Far

East and at higher latitudes [20]. However, the incidence of mucormycosis caused by various representatives of Mucorales (*Rhizopus*, *Rhizomucor*, *Mucor*, *Lichtheimia*, *Absidia*, etc.) has significantly increased by 2024, with mortality rates exceeding 40% and reaching nearly 100% in the case of disseminated forms [21]. The high virulence of these pathogens, resistance to most antifungal drugs in some species, and their suppression of immune responses exacerbate the danger of these infections, especially in at-risk groups (patients with diabetes, cancer, etc.). Despite the development of a PCR test for early diagnosis [22] and the discovery of a connection between weakened virulence in certain strains and the absence of the *set1* gene, mucormycosis remains a serious public health concern (March 2024). The inclusion of the entire order Mucorales, rather than just individual species, in the high-priority group reflects this complex epidemiological situation.

A similar approach was applied to the genus *Fusarium*, considering its wide distribution in nature and the presence of various pathogenic species that cause fusariosis. A more detailed specification of the species within the order Mucorales and genus *Fusarium* requires further research. *Candida tropicalis* is found in 5% of healthy women on the mucous membrane of the urogenital tract and in 2–3% of men and women in the large intestine. Its high virulence is due to biofilm formation, the secretion of lytic enzymes, and adhesion to cells. *C. tropicalis* rapidly develops resistance to fluconazole, so recurrent candidiasis requires combination antifungal therapy (at higher doses than for *C. albicans*) [23]. *C. tropicalis* can colonize tumors, affecting cancer treatment. Studies at Omsk Technical University have demonstrated the potential use of *C. tropicalis* for detoxifying distillery stillage and producing feed additives [24].

Candida parapsilosis accounts for 13% of *Candida* spp. isolates in invasive candidiasis cases (2023–2024). Its virulence is attributed to lipase and oxidase activity. Fluconazole resistance is linked to mutations in the *erg11* gene (10.8% in cancer patients), while echinocandin resistance is associated with mutations in the *fkp1* gene (20.3%). Sensitivity testing for antifungal drugs is necessary. This pathogen is associated with high mortality (17.5–46.8%) and morbidity, particularly among ICU patients, individuals over 65 years old, and infants younger than one year [16]. Invasive candidiasis can lead to septic shock and fatal outcomes, whereas antifungal resistance worsens prognosis and increases treatment costs.

Despite limited data on the prevalence of *Scedosporium* spp. in Russia, studies have indicated an increasing frequency of this fungal pathogen being isolated from the respiratory tract in patients over 14 years old (3.4–17.4%)

[25]. Infections affect the lungs (41.6%), eyes (33.3%), and other organs, including the vascular system (unpublished data, 2024), with high mortality rates (42.4–71.4%). The risk factors include organ transplantation and diabetes. The IMARC (International Mining and Resources Conference, 2024) market forecast predicts 5.8% growth in antifungal treatment by 2034, highlighting the need for new therapeutic strategies [4].

Data on the prevalence and impact of *Lomentospora prolificans* on public health in Russia remain insufficient, representing an area requiring further research. Infections caused by *L. prolificans* are characterized by high mortality (approximately 90% within 9 days of dissemination) and resistance to most antifungal drugs [26]. Early diagnosis and treatment, including olorofim administration, are crucial for reducing mortality. The disease can affect various organs, including the bones and joints, even in children. Risk factors for this disease include elevated levels of 1,3-beta-D-glucan and a history of antifungal prophylaxis [27].

Coccidioidomycosis, caused by *Coccidioides* spp., is not endemic to Russia, but the risk of importation of this infection is increasing. While most cases are asymptomatic, pneumonia, as well as skin and joint involvement, can develop [28]. The high virulence and stability of spores require attention, especially considering climate change. Recent studies have identified the Ryp1 protein as a key virulence factor [29]. There are no data on the prevalence of coccidioidomycosis in Russia, and its symptom similarity with other diseases complicates the diagnosis.

The prevalence of *Pneumocystis jirovecii* in Russia and the CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States) is high (45–88.5% infection rate in the adult population). Children at childcare institutions are particularly at risk. The peak incidence of pneumocystis pneumonia (*Pneumocystis jirovecii* pneumonia, PJP) in children occurs in late summer to early fall. Severe course of PJP is observed in immunocompromised adults [30, 31]. There is no official statistical data on this matter. Research is ongoing to identify mutant strains, develop new diagnostic methods, including the recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) method with Cas12a protein detection, and assess treatment efficacy. High PJP risk is observed in HIV-infected individuals with low CD4 cell counts, patients with idiopathic inflammatory myopathies (under immunosuppression), and those with rheumatic diseases [32–34].

As of 2024, *Cryptococcus gattii* had not been detected in Russia. It primarily affects individuals aged 40–60, with men being more frequently affected than women [23]. Severe disease involving the brain, meninges, and

Fig. 4. WHO Priority list of bacterial pathogens for 2024 [5].

skin can develop in immunocompromised patients. Risk factors for cryptococcosis caused by *C. gattii* include immunosuppression; cryptococcal immune reconstitution inflammatory syndrome (C-IRIS) may develop. Global prevalence accounts for 11-33% of invasive cryptococcosis cases [35].

There is no available information on the prevalence of talaromycosis (caused by *Talaromyces marneffeii*) in Russia. Talaromycosis is most observed in immunocompromised individuals (especially HIV-infected patients), causing

reticuloendothelial system involvement and respiratory and gastrointestinal symptoms [36]. Although the incidence among HIV-infected individuals has declined owing to antiretroviral therapy (ART), the number of cases is increasing among patients with other immunodeficiencies. Recent studies have identified fungal adaptation mechanisms and genetic risk factors for this disease [37]. Globalization increases the risk of *T. marneffeii* spreading beyond endemic regions (Southeast Asia).

Paracoccidioidomycosis, caused by fungi of the *Paracoccidioides* genus, is not observed in Russia; however, the risk of imported cases is increasing. Studies from 2024 have identified virulence factors of *Paracoccidioides* spp., including dimorphism, cell wall composition, production of metalloproteins and melanin, and biofilm formation, and have shed light on the role of α -glucans [38, 39].

Based on the evaluation results of 24 combinations of bacterial pathogens and pharmaceutical drugs, the former have been ranked and divided into three priority BPPL groups for 2024 (Fig. 4).

Gram-negative bacteria, especially carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* (CRAB) and carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales (CRE), are priority pathogens in BPPL-2024 because of their high virulence, limited therapeutic options, and high mortality of infections caused by these pathogens, particularly in hospitals [25, 40].

CRAB is a leading global pathogen; since 2017, no new effective antibiotics have been developed against strains that produce metallo- β -lactamases. CRE and third generation cephalosporin-resistant Enterobacterales (3GCRE) remain a priority because of their high prevalence and resistance, which causes significant economic damage. 3GCRE is a growing threat in low-income and middle-income countries [40]. The priority of CRPA (carbapenem-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) has been downgraded, but research and development (R&D) focused on new antibacterial agents against this pathogen remains critical due to high mortality rates among immunocompromised individuals [41, 42].

Resistance of Group A Streptococci to macrolides, Group B Streptococci to penicillin, and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* to macrolides is a serious concern, threatening effective treatment and infection control, particularly among vulnerable populations [43, 44].

Thus, the priority bacterial pathogens for 2024 are as follows.

- Critical Priority Group
 - *Acinetobacter baumannii* (carbapenem-resistant)
 - Enterobacterales (resistant to third generation cephalosporins)
 - Enterobacterales (carbapenem-resistant)
 - *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (rifampicin-resistant)
- High Priority Group:
 - *Salmonella* Typhi (fluoroquinolone-resistant)
 - *Shigella* spp. (fluoroquinolone-resistant)
 - *Enterococcus faecium* (vancomycin-resistant)
 - *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (carbapenem-resistant)
 - Nontyphoidal *Salmonella* (fluoroquinolone-resistant)

- *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* (resistant to third generation cephalosporins and/or fluoroquinolones)
- *Staphylococcus aureus* (methicillin-resistant)
- Medium Priority Group:
 - Group A Streptococci (macrolide-resistant)
 - *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (macrolide-resistant)
 - *Haemophilus influenzae* (ampicillin-resistant)
 - Group B Streptococci (penicillin-resistant)

Acinetobacter baumannii causes various infections, including respiratory and wound infections, bloodstream, urinary tract, and central nervous system infections. Risk factors include advanced age, immunodeficiencies (cancer, burns, and organ failure), and prolonged hospitalization [12]. Male sex was associated with an increased risk of infection. There are no accessible data on the prevalence of *A. baumannii* in Russia by 2024. The resistance of this bacterium to last-line antibiotics (tigecycline and polymyxin) is also increasing [45]. High antibiotic resistance and severity of infections caused by *A. baumannii* lead to high mortality and poor prognosis.

The lack of data on the prevalence of Enterobacterales resistant to third generation cephalosporins in Russia in 2024 hinders the assessment of the scale of this problem. Resistance increases mortality (by five times), length of hospitalization (by a factor of 1.5), and treatment costs; 10% of infections are caused by these bacteria in patients lacking risk factors. Data from 2024 indicate high cephalosporin resistance in *E. coli* (ranging from 36% to 64% depending on the specific drug). Enterobacterales (*E. coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) are classified as critical priority bacteria because of their high antibiotic resistance and the transmission of resistance genes [5, 46]. This situation is exacerbated by the spread of resistance to other antibiotics, including carbapenems (*Acinetobacter baumannii*) and rifampicin (*Mycobacterium tuberculosis*).

The prevalence of carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales is increasing in Russia. The MARATHON study revealed carbapenemase production in 14.4% of these bacterial strains, predominantly OXA-48 (75%, except those isolated in St. Petersburg, where NDM was more common). Various bacteria producing carbapenemases (NDM, OXA-48, and KPC) are widespread, with an increasing prevalence of KPC synthesizing microorganisms. The proportion of Enterobacterales among nosocomial infections has nearly doubled from 2011 to 2021 (from 31.8% to 56.4%). Infections caused by carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales have high mortality rates (2–3 times higher in cases of bacteremia and sepsis) and poor prognoses. Risk factors include

prior carbapenem therapy, high levels of carbapenemase-producing bacteria in hospital wards, intestinal colonization, and travel to regions with a high prevalence of carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales. Treatment is costly because of the high price of antibiotics and prolonged hospitalization, while increasing antibiotic resistance threatens the feasibility of complex medical procedures [47].

Data on the prevalence of fluoroquinolone-resistant *Salmonella* Typhi in Russia in 2024 are limited; however, between 2005 and 2017, typhoid fever was recorded in 19 regions (more than 70% of cases were imported), primarily among individuals aged 15–40 years. From 2005 to 2019, quinolone-resistant strains of the Asian clone with multiple mutations, resistant to fluoroquinolones and azithromycin, were predominant [48]. The spread of antibiotic resistance is associated with the widespread use of antibiotics. Poor sanitation facilitates the spread of this high-priority pathogen. The incidence of typhoid fever in Russia is sporadic; however, it remains a global problem (with over 16 million cases and 600,000 deaths annually worldwide). In Russia, the mortality rate of this disease is low (0.1–0.3%), but complications (10–15%) and recurrent infections are possible [5]. The high incidence of salmonellosis has led to significant economic loss.

Shigellosis (bacterial dysentery), caused by *Shigella* spp., has been recorded year-round, with a peak incidence in summer and fall. The incidence rate of shigellosis in Russia was 1.98 per 100,000 population in 2020. Most cases and deaths occur among children under five years of age and adults from socially disadvantaged groups. The spread of antibiotic resistance in *Shigella* spp. is associated with the horizontal transfer of resistance genes between the strains. Resistance of these bacteria to antibiotics (ciprofloxacin, cephalosporins, azithromycin) is increasing, reducing treatment effectiveness, and increasing mortality (over 500,000 deaths annually worldwide) [11, 49].

Vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecium* (VREfm) was detected in all federal districts of Russia in 2017–2020, with the highest prevalence in St. Petersburg. Studies have shown that VREfm accounts for a significant proportion of bloodstream infections in oncology patients. These bacteria show higher vancomycin resistance in adults than in children. VREfm is a difficult-to-treat nosocomial pathogen often associated with treatment failure and relapse. Linezolid is used to treat vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE). VREfm causes infections more frequently than VRE *faecalis* and is associated with high mortality rates (up to 50% or more in critical conditions and up to 80% in neutropenic

patients). Prolonged hospitalization, catheterization, and colonization contribute to the spread of VREfm, increasing the treatment duration and costs [50].

There are no available data on the prevalence of carbapenem-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (CRPA) in Russia as of 2024. *P. aeruginosa* is a common cause of nosocomial infections (18.6% in 2020), including sepsis, pneumonia, urinary tract infections, intra-abdominal infections, and wound infections. Carbapenem-resistant *P. aeruginosa* is particularly dangerous in patients with cystic fibrosis [1]. The spread of CRPA is associated with the development of drug resistance due to mutations and transmission of resistance genes. Despite WHO's assessment of a reduced global threat, the high mortality rate (up to 50%) and significant treatment costs necessitate further research and preventive measures. The increase in hospital-acquired infections has driven demand for the treatment of infections caused by CRPA [5].

In 2020, the incidence of salmonellosis decreased by 1.6 times compared to that in 2019, reaching 14.7 per 100,000 population. Salmonellosis is recorded year-round, with a peak incidence in the summer and fall. Between 2019 and 2022, the proportion of fluoroquinolone-resistant *Salmonella* strains among isolates from humans, animals, and food products reached 50–60%. In 2024, fluoroquinolone resistance among non-typhoidal *Salmonella* increased. Antibiotic-resistant *Salmonella* strains cause severe illnesses, increasing the risk of hospitalization, sepsis, and death (up to 15% in the case of invasive infections) [51]. The spread of resistance, which leads to significant economic losses, is associated with the widespread use of antibiotics and inadequate sanitation.

The prevalence of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) in Russia varies widely (0–80%), with asymptomatic colonization observed in 30–60% of the population. MRSA poses a significant threat to patients with diabetes, street drug users, individuals taking quinolones, children, the elderly, and health care workers. High resistance to fluoroquinolones and cefoxitin, along with reduced susceptibility to ceftaroline, limit treatment options. MRSA is more virulent and causes severe infections (sepsis, shock, pneumonia) with a mortality rate 60% higher than that of methicillin-sensitive infections [52]. The WHO classifies MRSA as a priority pathogen.

In 2024, FSOCPW reported a decline in 65 nosological forms of infectious diseases, including scarlet fever. Respiratory infections (pharyngitis, tonsillitis) dominate temperate and cold climate zones, with a peak in winter and spring, particularly among young schoolchildren. In

the southern regions, skin infections (impetigo) are more common and primarily affect children aged 2–6 years from low-income families. Group A *Streptococcus* causes a range of infections, from mild (pharyngitis, impetigo) to severe and life-threatening (necrotizing fasciitis, sepsis, and toxic shock syndrome). Increasing resistance of *Streptococcus pyogenes* to macrolides reduces the effectiveness of treatment. There was an increase in severe infections following the lifting of COVID-19 restrictions, including scarlet fever, which was linked to the new M1_{UK} variant. Additional research is required to develop new strategies to combat the resistance of these bacteria.

There has been a decline in *Streptococcus pneumoniae* susceptibility to β -lactams and macrolides in Russia. Macrolide resistance levels vary by region (6–25%), while resistance to tetracycline, azithromycin, and erythromycin is approximately 25% among adults [53]. Ceftaroline, respiratory fluoroquinolones, vancomycin, and linezolid remain effective against *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The high-risk groups include children, the elderly, and patients with chronic conditions. Risk factors for resistance include antibiotic use, prior illness, and hospitalization. Invasive infections are severe, with a mortality rate of approximately 20% and disability of approximately 60%, and most frequently affect adults [5].

The incidence of *Haemophilus influenzae* infection is higher in winter and spring. The high-risk groups include children aged 6 months to 4 years (especially under 2 years), daycare children, formula-fed infants, as well as children from non-European ethnic groups and low socio-economic groups. The prevalence of ampicillin-resistant strains has decreased from 10.1% (2004–2016) to 2.1% (2023). Treatment options include β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitors, third generation cephalosporins, co-trimoxazole, macrolides, fluoroquinolones, and tetracycline. Invasive infections (meningitis and bacteremia) in children under four years of age have high mortality rates (up to 40% in sepsis) and a risk of neurological complications (15–35%) [54]. Ampicillin resistance increases the treatment costs.

In Moscow, the prevalence of group B *Streptococcus* (GBS) among outpatients is 4.3%, most commonly affecting women aged 24–39 years. GBS causes severe illnesses, especially in newborns (incidence of 0.5–5 per 1,000 births), pregnant women, and immunocompromised individuals. Mortality among newborns can reach 10% and disability rates can reach up to 50% [55]. The antibiotic resistance of GBS (penicillin and tetracycline) is increasing, but these bacteria remain susceptible to other antibiotics (linezolid, erythromycin, clindamycin,

teicoplanin, vancomycin) [56]. The resistance levels vary across countries.

DISCUSSION

The present study revealed a discrepancy between the mortality rate of infections caused by antimicrobial-resistant pathogens and the volume of investment in R&D aimed at finding new therapies against them. This discrepancy is particularly noticeable in relation to common pathogens, such as *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Candida albicans*, which, despite causing infections with high mortality rates, receive less attention in the development of new drugs compared to rare but highly lethal pathogens, such as *Lomentospora prolificans*. This situation requires reassessment of R&D funding strategies to prioritize the most widespread and deadly infections.

Analysis of bacterial pathogens has confirmed the critical need for the development of new antimicrobial drugs against gram-negative bacteria (CRAB, CRE, and 3GCRE) because of their high virulence and limited therapeutic options for treating infections caused by these bacteria. Despite a potential decrease in carbapenem resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in some regions, the demand for R&D focused on new antimicrobials against this bacterium remains high, especially for treating immunocompromised patients. Similarly, the growing resistance to fluoroquinolones and other antibiotics in *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Enterococcus faecium*, and streptococci requires comprehensive measures, including increased funding for research and development of new antibiotics, improved infection control strategies, and global resistance monitoring.

Based on the obtained data, we consider it necessary to conduct a deeper analysis of the epidemiological aspects of antimicrobial resistance in Russia. It is essential to study the possible sources of infection outbreaks, pathogen transmission routes, and factors that contribute to the development of resistance. This will enable the development of more effective strategies for prevention and control of drug-resistant infections. It is also necessary to consider the regional specifics of pathogen distribution and socioeconomic factors affecting access to medical care. Conducting prospective international studies with an expanded database is key to gaining a more comprehensive understanding of resistance mechanisms and developing new therapeutic strategies. Only a comprehensive approach that considers all these aspects will allow for an effective reduction in mortality from infections caused by antimicrobial-resistant pathogens.

CONCLUSION

The present study identified a significant public health threat in Russia associated with an increasing incidence of fungal and bacterial infections caused by pathogens that are resistant to antimicrobial agents. Data analysis has shown that among fungal pathogens, the greatest threats are presented by *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Lomentospora prolificans*, *Pneumocystis jirovecii*, *Candida auris*, and fungi of the order Mucorales, which are characterized by high mortality, widespread prevalence, or significant resistance to therapy. Special attention should be given to *Candida auris*, which causes nosocomial infections with high fatality rates. The lack of data on the prevalence of certain pathogens, especially *Lomentospora prolificans*, highlights the urgent need to strengthen epidemiological surveillance.

A similar situation has been observed for bacterial infections. Our data indicate a high risk associated with the spread of CRE, MRSA, VREfm, CRPA, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, fluoroquinolone-resistant *Salmonella* Typhi and *Shigella* spp., Group A streptococci, *Streptococcus*

pneumoniae, and *Haemophilus influenzae*. Infections caused by these pathogens have high mortality rates, account for significant economic burden, and, additionally, there is a lack of effective treatment options for them. The absence of comprehensive data on the prevalence of some of these pathogens, such as *Acinetobacter baumannii* in 2024, underscores the critical need to strengthen the epidemiological surveillance system in Russia.

Based on our analysis, we conclude that comprehensive measures are necessary to prevent morbidity and mortality due to infections caused by antimicrobial-resistant pathogens. These measures should include strengthening epidemiological surveillance, developing effective strategies to combat antimicrobial resistance, and expanding the research on new diagnostic and treatment methods for infectious diseases.

Additional information that provides a broader understanding of certain aspects of this study can be found in these publications [57-63].

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